

Supplemental Note for using heritage LEO lightning instruments in the SAA:

The thresholds presented in this study were designed to isolate the SAA signal for three heritage optical lightning instruments in low-Earth orbit, conservative in favor of only capturing the SAA and eliminating other potential causes of interference. The thresholds were as follows, accumulated at a monthly rate: instrument warning flag (called VA flag in study) was tripped in $\geq 40\%$ of observations for TRMM-LIS, activated ≥ 5 times per observation for ISS-LIS, and where the first-in first-out (FIFO) buffer overflow was active in $\geq 10\%$ of overpasses for OTD. These thresholds were used to map the most consistent SAA-attributable interference but are not necessarily suitable for filtering out potentially degraded observations on a per-orbit basis. However, for climatological purposes that accumulate over longer periods, these metrics could be appropriate. OTD detection efficiency corrections were developed by Christian et al. (2003) for within the SAA and are recommended to be used for correcting climatological flash rates in the vicinity of the SAA. Depending on the purpose, the recommended bounds for the LIS thresholds are $40\% \geq X \geq 20\%$ for TLIS, and $5 \geq X \geq 3$ counts for ILIS. The authors recommend the lower thresholds when the goal is to identify any potentially degraded observations, understanding that the flagged patterns may not be spatially contiguous, and the higher thresholds when exclusively focusing on SAA interference.

For the LIS instruments, effective observation time is the most appropriate metric to identify reductions in observational capability on a per-orbit basis. One method presented by Cecil et al. (2015) discarded observations where the underlying effective observation time per overpass was less than 80-s, given that the nominal observation time should be ~ 90 -s per observation for the LIS instruments. In effect, this is a per-orbit application of the lost view-time product, and the threshold minimum observation time can be tailored to best suit the needs of the desired outcome. This method is generally conservative, also eliminating observations along the edges of the swath. It also does not represent the pre-boost TRMM record well (granted- there was no discernable SAA interference then anyway) and can be quite noisy in the ISS record since the observation times are not as predictable as those for TLIS. That said, it is a quick and practical way to get clean data. Note, however, that the effective observation time should not be used as a correction factor (e.g., if $f = 5$ flashes are observed, and the effective observation time was 60-s, $f_c \neq (90/60) * 5$) due to sampling constraints. Furthermore, preliminary results indicate that view-time losses impact sub-flash characteristics, (e.g., event count, extent) more than the actual flash count.

References

Cecil, D. J., D. E. Buechler, and R. J. Blakeslee, 2015: TRMM LIS climatology of thunderstorm occurrence and conditional lightning flash rates. *J. Clim.*, **28 (16)**, 6536–6547, [https://doi.org/ 10.1175/JCLI-D-15-0124.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JCLI-D-15-0124.1).

Christian, H. J., and Coauthors, 2003: Global frequency and distribution of lightning as observed from space by the Optical Transient Detector. *J. Geophys. Res.*, **108, D1**, 4005, doi: 10.1029/2002JD002347.